

Paper 22

THE STUDY OF PSYCHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS ON FEMALE VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

Ashwini Venkanagouda Patil^{1*} and Dr. Hanumanthayya Pujari²

¹Research Scholar, Department of physical education and sports sciences, Karnataka State Women's University, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India-586108.

^{1*} corresponding author, e-mail address: ashwiniv.patil90@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, Department of physical education, Vijayanagara Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Bellary, Karnataka, India- 583105.

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of psychological parameters on female volleyball players in the age group of 16 to 18 years. In this investigation, a total of 12 female players from SDM sports hostel, Ujire, Mangalore participated. Anthropometric and psychological measurements were recorded and analyzed. Basic anthropometric parameters like age, height and weight were recorded. Players responses to 27 questionnaires were documented. For psychological study, anxiety and self-confidence measurements were taken. Anxieties like cognitive anxiety and somatic anxiety were analyzed. The recorded data has been interpreted to determine the psychological status of the players.

Keywords: Psychological parameters, volleyball.

1.INTRODUCTION

When the volleyball players are subjected to extreme physical activities in training sessions and matches, maintaining calmness and patience becomes the requirements [1]. The psychological status of a player plays a crucial role here. Getting hold in this psychological profile, a player should have acceptable anthropometric profile [2, 3 and 4]. In psychology study of a player, anxiety and confidence holds the important factor [5]. Illinois competition test was conducted to know the anxiety and confidence levels of the players. Competitive state anxiety inventory – II (CSAI-II) have 27 statements to be recorded. The responses to these 27 statements or questions were recorded to know the feelings of the player. The purpose of this study is to know the player's anxiety levels, confidence levels, the psychological status and finally, the impact of anthropometric and psychological parameters on the female volleyball players.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS AND DISCUSSION

In this investigation, female student players from SDM sports hostel, Ujire, Mangalore (under 18 category-female) were taken. To know the anxiety level of volleyball players, each one of the players were asked to respond to 27 questions with 4 optional responses. This set of questions is known as Illinois Competition Test. Minimum of 9 to maximum of 36 can be scored by a player and that score will help us to know the anxiety levels and self-confidence level. In addition to the above psychological measurements their age (years), height (in centimetre) and weight (in kilogram) were recorded.

Table 1: The Anthropometric and psychological measurements of female volleyball players.

<i>Players No.</i>	<i>Age (yrs)</i>	<i>Height (cm)</i>	<i>Weight (kg)</i>	<i>Cognitive state anxiety</i>	<i>Somatic state anxiety</i>	<i>Self-confidence</i>
<i>Player 1</i>	18	154	43	30	25	31
<i>Player 2</i>	17	166	56	29	25	31
<i>Player 3</i>	17	169	52	33	19	35
<i>Player 4</i>	16	169	58	35	29	36
<i>Player 5</i>	17	165	50	33	25	31
<i>Player 6</i>	18	169	51	34	21	31
<i>Player 7</i>	16	152	44	25	21	33
<i>Player 8</i>	18	170	51	32	23	30
<i>Player 9</i>	16	155	42	31	25	31
<i>Player 10</i>	18	171	57	34	25	35
<i>Player 11</i>	16	161	46	29	20	30
<i>Player 12</i>	17	167	55	27	19	31

Table 2: The Questionnaire or the Illinois Competition Test questions for female volleyball players.

<u>Q. No.</u>	<u>Statements - Question</u>	<u>Q. No.</u>	<u>Statements - Question</u>
1.	I am concerned about this competition.	15.	I'm confident I can meet the challenge.
2.	I feel nervous.	16.	I'm concerned about performing poorly.
3.	I feel at ease.	17.	My heart is racing.
4.	I have self-doubts.	18.	I'm confident about performing well.
5.	I feel jittery.	19.	I'm worried about reaching my goal.
6.	I feel comfortable.	20.	I feel my stomach sinking.
7.	I am concerned I may not do as well in this competition as I could.	21.	I feel mentally relaxed.
8.	My body feels tense.	22.	I'm concerned that others will be disappointed with my performance.
9.	I feel self-confident.	23.	My hands are clammy.

10.	I am concerned about losing.	24.	I'm confident because I mentally picture myself reaching my goal.
11.	I feel tense in my stomach.	25.	I'm concerned I won't be able to concentrate.
12.	I feel secure.	26.	My body feels tight.
13.	I am concerned about losing.	27.	I'm confident of coming through under pressure.
14.	My body feels relaxed.		

Table 1 shows anthropometric and psychological measurements of the female volleyball players. In order to know the anxiety and confidence levels, Illinois competition test, competitive state anxiety inventory – II (CSAI-II), was conducted. Here the players were exposed to 27 statements to which they have to reply with any one of four responses. The 27 statements are listed in Table 2. The four responses were: Not at all (score 1), somewhat (score 2), moderately so (score 3) and very much so (score 4). All the scores of 27 statements were added to get in between minimum score of 9 to maximum score of 36. However, for statement no. 14, scores were inverted from 4 to 1 in the response. Cognitive state anxiety was recorded taking the sum of replies from statements 1, 4, 7, 10, 13, 16, 19, 22 and 25. Somatic state anxiety was recorded taking the sum of replies from statements 2, 5, 8, 11, 14 (inverted response score), 17, 20, 23 and 26. Self-confidence was recorded taking the sum of replies from statements 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24 and 27.

By looking into table 1, player no. 4 and 10 have not only shown good anthropometric profiles but also have shown positive anxiety and self-confidence scores. In fact all the players of the team are having good scores in cognitive anxiety and self confidence. Cognitive anxiety representing mental anxiety status of the players is quite healthy. But somatic or physical anxiety status is just average with not more than 29+ score because of the fact that players are subjected to extreme physical activities in training and matches. As the game demand extreme physical activities, players are supposed to have an good anthropometric and psychological profiles.

3.CONCLUSION

Psychological status of a player influences the game proceedings and also the game result. Psychology profile can be good only if a player is first maintaining a healthy anthropometric profile. Players self confidence levels were found to be exceptionally positive when compared to their anxiety levels. Especially somatic anxiety, also known as physical anxiety, was found to be low. However, Cognitive anxiety, known as mental anxiety, was found to be above average value of 18+ score. This shows the team is having acceptable high self confidence level, which is required by any player/team. And with the score just more than average value of 18+, the anxiety level is also acceptable. This is because the team is not having low score indicating low anxiety and high score indicating high anxiety, which in both cases leads to undesirable game results. Maintaining the optimal range of anxiety score will be suitable and helpful for a player.

4.ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I sincerely thank all the staff members and research scholars of department of physical education and sports sciences, Karnataka State Women's University, Vijayapura, Karnataka, India for their support and encouragement towards this paper.

REFERENCES

1. Marques MC, van den Tillaar R, Gabbett T, Reis VM, González-Badillo JJ, Physical fitness qualities of professional volleyball players: determination of positional differences, *Journal of Strength Cond. Res.*, 2009 ; no. 23, 2009, pages 1106–1111.
2. J. Pena, D. Moreno-Doutres, J. Coma, M. Cook, B. Busca, Anthropometric and fitness profile of high level basketball, handball and volleyball players, *MedicinadelDeporte, Rev Andal Med Deporte* 11(1), 2018: pg. 30-35.
3. Liliana dacica, The formative role of physical education and sports, *Procedia - Social and behavioral sciences* 180, 2015: pg. 1242-1247.
4. Liliana elisabetaradu, FatihHazar, Alexandrurarespuni, Anthropometric and Physical fitness characteristics of university students, *Procedia - Social and behavioral sciences* 149, 2014: pg. 798-802.
5. Juan Mielgo Ayuso, Michael C. Zourdos, Vicente J. Clemente Suárez, Julio Calleja González, Amber M. Shipherd, Can psychological well-being scales and hormone levels be used to predict acute performance of anaerobic training tasks in elite female volleyball players?, *Physiology & Behavior*, Volume 180, 15 October 2017, pg. 31-38.